

October 5, 2023

Psychosocial Adjustment in Young Millennials

A Data Management Plan created with DMP Assistant

Data Management Planning Expert Group

Information

Summary

This data management plan was created using the Portage template for mixed methods (surveys and qualitative research) offered on the DMP Assistant platform. It was developed by a team of researchers and a research advisor with support from the research data management working group of the communauté de pratique des conseillères et conseillers à la recherche [research advisors' community of practice], which is led by the Association pour la recherche au collégial. It was created in response to an invitation from the Digital Research Alliance of Canada's Data Management Planning Expert Group (DMPEG) to create sample data management plans (DMPs) that could be shared publicly to help researchers develop high-quality DMPs. The plan concerns innovative social practice research conducted by a college technology transfer centre. It uses a mixed methodology combining quantitative analysis of secondary and primary survey data with analysis of qualitative data collected from one-on-one interviews.

Administrative details

Project name: Psychosocial Adjustment in Young Millennials

Creator: Julie Auclair, Marie-Ève Blackburn and Marie Briand

Principal investigator: Marie-Ève Blackburn

Institution: Cégep de Jonquière, Saguenay, Canada.

Funding agency: Fonds de recherche du Québec – Société et culture (FRQSC)

Template: Portage Template for Mixed Methods (Surveys and Qualitative Research)

Description: The research project aims to improve our understanding of the various ways in which a group of millennials have adapted to adulthood. The proposed methodology uses a mixed-method approach combining quantitative analysis of longitudinal data, with an online survey developed by the Centre d'Étude des COnditions de vie et des BESoins de la population (ÉCOBES) [Centre to study population needs and living conditions] and one-on-one interviews to expand on the findings from the quantitative analysis. Data from an ongoing study launched in 2002, a survey of Saguenay–Lac-Saint-Jean students who were aged 14 in 2002 (ELESJ), will be analyzed to identify various psychosocial coping strategies used by youth aged 14 to 24. The findings from these analyses will then be used to reconnect with the entire cohort. A mass mail message will be sent to each of the 384 ELESJ participants. A personalized portrait (two double-sided pages) of each participant will be included in this mass mailing. The message will contain a link to an online questionnaire to fill out with multiple scales measuring various dimensions. Fifty ELESJ respondents will subsequently be invited to take part in one-on-one

interviews to better understand key moments in their life and identify the psychosocial coping mechanisms used in their transition to adulthood.

Digital Research
Alliance of Canada

Alliance de recherche
numérique du Canada

Research Data Management Policies

Are there research data management policies that outline data management requirements or best practices? If applicable, please specify and provide URL links to these policies.

The CEGEP has policies and reference documents that at least partially govern research data management:

- [Ethics policy for research involving humans](#) [in French]
- [Responsible conduct of research policy](#) [in French]
- [Information asset security policy](#) [in French]
- [Intellectual property policy](#) [in French]
- Document management policy and record retention schedule

The Centre collégial de transfert de technologie ÉCOBES [ÉCOBES college technology transfer centre] has developed two research methodology guides, one for quantitative analysis and the other for qualitative analysis, as well as a guide to using the record management system.

Other policies are also relevant to this type of research:

- [Tri-Council Policy Statement: Ethical Conduct for Research Involving Humans \(TCPS 2\)](#)
- [First Nations Information Governance Centre Principles of OCAP®](#)

Data Collection

Describe which types of data you will collect, including any data from surveys, interviews and focus groups. If other types of data will be collected or generated, describe this data as well.

Quantitative data:

Data will be collected via an online questionnaire conducted using survey software (LimeSurvey). This questionnaire will include several scales to measure the factors being studied: socio-demographic variables, the school-to-work-transition, psychological health, support, the impact of the pandemic, etc.. This data will then be transferred in .dat or .csv format to the statistical analysis software IBM SPSS Statistics (.sav format) and SAS software (.sas format) to carry out other types of analysis.

Qualitative data:

Data will be collected from semi-structured 45- to 60-minute interviews (expected number of interviews: 30 to 50). All interviews will be conducted by telephone (recorded in .mp3, .m4a, .amr or .mp4 format). They will be transcribed verbatim in Microsoft Word (.docx) and processed using Nvivo content analysis software (.nvp).

Is there existing data that can be reused to answer one of your research questions? If so, please describe how this data will be obtained and incorporated into your research project.

Data collected by ÉCOBES in 2002, 2004, 2006 and 2012 will be reused. Participants provided consent for use of this secondary data. The project was approved by the research ethics board in 2002 for data collection from 2002 to 2006 and for each subsequent data collection phase. A copy of the original data will be made and identified as a secondary source for this project.

It is important to specify and understand which data collection methods you will use as early as possible to ensure they meet your needs, including for the secure collection of sensitive data, if applicable. Describe the data collection methods you will use.

Emailing a link that is directly associated with each participant will allow them to complete the online survey on LimeSurvey if they choose to do so. The data gathered will subsequently be transferred to SPSS Statistics and SAS software, as applicable. Qualitative data from telephone interviews will be recorded using a digital audio device, transferred to the CEGEP's secure servers and erased from the digital audio device once the transfer is complete.

If audio recordings of interviews or focus groups will be transcribed, describe how this will be done securely, particularly whether they will be transcribed by the research team or externally (subcontracted) or if a software program, platforms or electronic services will be used for transcription purposes.

The digital audio files transferred directly to the CEGEP's secure server (via USB) will be listened to and transcribed by ÉCOBES group research assistants employed by the institution. They will use WORD for transcription. All transcriptions will be made using confidential files created for the purpose. Source recordings and transcriptions in the directory created on the network will be protected by the fact that only members of the research project team have access to these folders. Members who work with confidential data, including research assistants, must first complete basic training in research ethics and sign a confidentiality agreement.

Describe how your data will be transferred securely, particularly from data collection devices or platforms and to or from transcribers, as applicable.

LimeSurvey is a secure online survey platform whose data is hosted in Canada and that meets the data security requirements of the institution's research ethics committee. Survey data will be directly transferred from the LimeSurvey platform to the institution's secure servers and processed only by those servers. In accordance with new guidance from the information resource department, the data will be erased from LimeSurvey's public platform after being transferred. From that point on, it is only accessible via computers that are part of the institution's network. Interviews will be recorded and transferred to the secure server and erased from the digital audio recorder.

Describe all file formats that your data will exist in, including different versions of data from surveys, qualitative interviews or focus groups. Will these formats support long-term re-use of, sharing of and access to the data?

Research data can be generated in many different formats. It is important to understand as soon as possible which formats your research data will exist in. This will be helpful on numerous fronts, including estimating data size and storage requirements, identifying any software needed to read and work with the data and following best practices for long-term data preservation and access.

Raw quantitative data will be available in the following format: .dat

Raw and processed quantitative data will be available in the following formats: .csv, .sav, .sas, .xlsx

Final quantitative data will be stored for re-use in the following formats: .sav (Unicode mode), .csv.

Raw qualitative data will be available in the following formats: .mp3, .m4a, .amr

Processed qualitative data will be available in the following formats: .docx, .nvp.

Final qualitative data will be stored for re-use in the following format: Plain text.

Final data will be stored in open formats to ensure that the data can be re-used, shared and accessed in the long term.

Documentation and Metadata

Describe all documentation and metadata that will be used to ensure that the data can be read and understood during the active phases of the project and in the future.

Three documents will be produced to ensure that the data can be understood by a third party. The first will document the data collection methodology used (quantitative and qualitative) and will include the following information:

- Study population
- Date
- Context
- Sampling strategy
- Locations
- Collection characteristics

The second will document the measures taken:

- Interview grid
- Questionnaires
- Question sources

A third document will take the form of a “codebook” and will be used to document the quantitative database. It will include the following information for each field (variable):

- Name of variable
- Value label
- Calculation method (summarized in words or in SPSS syntax)
- Correspondence with collection instrument
- Variable status (raw or calculated)
- How non-responses will be handled
- Variable label

A unique identifier assigned to each statistical unit will allow qualitative data to be paired with quantitative data.

Describe the file naming conventions that will be used to assist with file quality assurance and version management and help others understand how your data is organized.

ÉCOBES has a user guide for the document management system, which was updated in 2022 and includes a section about standardizing file and directory names. The consistent naming system makes it possible to locate files quickly and easily, prevents duplicates and provides everything needed to search for files without overcomplicating the title.

Source data is stored under the original file name in a directory named Source. A copy of this file is made and placed in another directory named Data. The file is renamed in accordance with the following standards: AnalysisProjectName_Date (year-month-day in numbers). As data preparation progresses, a backup copy is placed in the VPrelim directory and the main database is renamed according to the date it was modified.

For quantitative databases processed using statistical analysis software, syntax files for processing, modifying or querying the database are filed in a directory called Processing and named according to the No-L-Objective standard, where L refers to the type of operation performed on the database, M refers to modification and E refers to exploration. Objective refers to the aim of the syntax file.

Describe how you will ensure that documents and metadata will be created, entered and, if applicable, updated consistently throughout the research project.

First, data collection details will be recorded in a logbook as the data is collected. This will contain information about the interview process, the interviewer's impressions, etc. These notes will be stored in a directory on the ÉCOBES internal network, often found in the confidential section of the project and named Terrain. Secondly, when the collection instruments are being designed, the sources of the questions that make up the interview grids and questionnaires will be systematically retained. Finally, when the data is received and processed (once data collection is complete), a methodological procedure will determine the approach taken and the order of operations applied to the data (modifications and queries) and enable thorough documentation of each stage. A master file will document changes to the database (purpose, decision, author, data, file names). Syntaxes for modifying and querying the database and traces of these operations are stored in files containing all the outputs.

Describe the metadata standards and tools that you will use to describe and document your data.

The research team is considering using the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) standard <https://ddialliance.org/>, a free standard that guarantees documents are consistent, structured and machine-readable, which is essential for data repositories and makes documents easily discoverable by search engines.

Storage, Access and Backup

Describe where, how and how long the data will be securely stored during the active phases of the research project. If the data must be collected using electronic platforms, explain how they will be used in your description. Describe all policies and procedures that will be implemented to ensure the data is backed up regularly.

The information resource department has already established a backup procedure, including recovery tests. Daily and weekly incremental copies and monthly and annual summary copies are made. During a project's active phase, data is stored in a mode that is accessible to all approved members of the research team for the project in question. The data is then archived (the access rights are modified) for semi-active phase of two years, during which only the principal investigator may access it. Finally, the data is stored for a renewable five-year period. In this final phase, data may only be accessed by a person authorized by the research ethics committee. In each of these phases, the data is stored on the institution's secure servers.

Describe how members of the research team will access and work with the data securely in the active phases of the research project.

ÉCOBES has a protocol governing staff access to the secure server. All ÉCOBES files are stored on a secure network drive and staff members must save their professional files to this disc only. Password authentication is required to access this disc, and each staff member may only access directories they have the right to access. A protocol is in place to manage requests for restricted access to the secure server's various directories. Access is always granted in read and write mode; however, any files considered confidential (e.g., qualitative databases and quantitative databases with personally identifiable information) are localized in a highly restricted directory that can only be accessed by individuals who are required to work there. Additionally, while full-time technicians and professionals have access to all project files (excluding confidential files), research assistants and any other temporary or part-time staff can only access project-specific directories and data to which they have been assigned. The principal investigator is responsible for access requests, as they are familiar with each team member's role. Due to their roles, ÉCOBES management and support staff and the CEGEP's IT department staff can access the entire network drive.

Describe the storage space you will need during the active phases of the research project, taking file version management and data growth into account.

The full project will require approximately 75 gigabytes of storage space for project and data management files. However, the files that will be shared on a data repository site will require one gigabyte at most.

Understanding the size and scope of your research data helps you identify both active storage needs and long-term data repository and preservation needs.

Preservation

Describe how you will ensure that your data is ready for retention, including the file formats they will be stored in, and explain how you will prevent data loss when files are processed and converted.

Quantitative data will be stored in the following two formats: .sav (Unicode mode) and .cvs. Quantitative data will be stored in the following two formats: .nvp and plain text. Plain text and .cvs format are open formats that facilitate re-use but result in a loss of information. To offset this loss, an accompanying README file will be provided. This will document the migration (software used, including the software version and operating system) and information lost, if any.

Describe where you will store your data long term, including the research data repositories you intend to use. Please specify if there is a cost associated with storing your data.

The data will be stored on a secure server belonging to the institution. Additionally, the research unit is following the progress of discussions between the Fédération des cégeps and the university libraries of Quebec, under the umbrella of the Bureau de coopération interuniversitaire (BCI), to come to an agreement to make the Borealis data repository accessible to the CEGEP network. If this agreement is signed, storing project data in the Borealis repository would be considered. The Borealis repository is free and open-source. Currently, we are unsure whether subscription fees will apply.

Sharing and Reuse

Describe the data you will share and specify the version (i.e., raw, processed, analyzed) and format.

Quantitative and qualitative data that has been processed and is ready for analysis may be shared. For this reason, verbatim transcripts, interview reports and quantitative source data will not be shared.

Any data shared will be de-identified. Names, addresses and any potentially identifying information will be removed.

Describe whether any restrictions will apply to your data when it is made available and who will be able to access it. If the data is not publicly available, describe the procedure to obtain access.

Currently, the data is not publicly available. ÉCOBES has implemented a quantitative data file sharing procedure. External researchers and students who would like to obtain a copy of the database can do so by indicating their research objective, variables of interest and requirements. Only data for which research participants have consented to secondary use and that has been approved by the institution's research ethics board may be shared. A copy of the database is sent to the researcher or student who made the request, excluding personally identifiable information or information not relevant to the request. Depending on the level of confidentiality, the files may be encrypted by a member of the research team using 7-Zip software before being sent by email. This software was selected because it meets the CEGEP de Jonquière information resource department's secure information transmission procedure requirements. Sharing is subject to the following conditions:

- Any data transmitted must only be used for the purpose specified in this application.
- Any data transmitted may not be transferred to a third party nor made available to anyone not listed in this application.
- Measures must be taken to restrict access to the data transmitted to the requesting parties. These measures must be outlined and transmitted to ÉCOBES for approval in writing.
- Research data must be used in a manner that respects the privacy of research participants and protects their personal information.
- The applicant undertakes to destroy the database and any copies of it no later than 12 months after the last communication or publication using the data transmitted and to inform ÉCOBES in writing once this has been done.

If the institution has a Borealis repository, the data for which research participants have consented to secondary use may be stored there, subject to the approval of the institution's research ethics board. Implementing a restricted access feature to review data access requests

as they are received is currently being considered. This would give individuals approved by the principal investigator access to Borealis.

Qualitative data is not currently being shared due to confidentiality issues and the risk of identification. However, we are currently exploring whether it might be possible to establish conditions and a procedure to enable this data to be shared.

What type of end-user licence will be selected for your data?

No decision has been made about the end-user licence. Discussions are underway to determine the type of licence that will be used.

Responsibilities and Resources

Who will be responsible for data management over the course of the project (i.e., collection, processing, analysis and documentation)? Describe the roles and responsibilities of each staff member in implementing the data management plan (DMP), including timeframes and training needs.

The institution has a research data management committee made up of individuals from the following departments:

- Research and innovation office
- Information resource department
- Archive and document management department
- Library
- Research ethics committee
- ÉCOBES college technology transfer centre

This committee has established an institutional strategy for research data management that will come into effect in March 2023.

For this research project, multiple individuals will be responsible for data sharing and retention. Ultimately, the principal investigator is responsible for ensuring that the data is retained and shared appropriately with the support of the institution's research data management committee. Concretely, the researcher will be responsible for updating the data management plan, training members of their team to implement the data management plan and facilitating research team meetings relating to RDM. The following members of the research team will be tasked with applying the data management plan:

- the collection coordinator and any research staff involved in collection
- the social research technician and analysts (quantitative and qualitative data)
- the research assistants

How will you delegate responsibility for data management activities if there are significant staffing changes, particularly a change in principal investigator?

Project data will be documented to ensure it can be transferred if necessary and managed effectively and appropriately. If a member of the research team, particularly the principal investigator, had to leave the project, ÉCOBES management would decide who would be responsible for data management in accordance with the institution's procedures.

What resources will you require to implement your data management plan? What is the approximate overall cost of data management?

Multiple steps will need to be taken to meet funding body requirements and implement the data management plan:

1. Training and familiarization with various metadata standards
2. Developing metadata tools (models to build), adjusting current protocols and transferring them to the research team
3. Completing metadata tools:
 - Documenting the collection methodology (terrain)
 - Documenting collection instruments
 - Documenting the quantitative database
 - Documenting the qualitative database

A total of 300 hours will be required to document the data, 183 of which will be used to meet new requirements for long-term data storage and retention. Most of these work hours will be split between research professionals and technicians, with some hours worked by research assistants. The estimated cost of the new data management requirements for this project is \$10,000.

Ethics and Legal Compliance

If applicable, what strategies will you use to address the secondary use of data, particularly data of a sensitive nature?

The information and consent forms for participants in the longitudinal survey, which is a secondary data source for the current project, contain two separate statements, one to provide consent to participate in the ongoing research project and another to consent to the secondary use of the data. The consent form for the secondary use of data specifies that:

- The data may only be used for social science research
- Only de-identified data may be re-used
- No personally identifiable information may be re-used

How will you handle legal, ethical and intellectual property issues?

The principal investigator will be responsible for handling legal, ethical and intellectual property issues that fall within their authority. In other situations or when in doubt, they can contact the CEGEP de Jonquière's Research and Innovation Office, which can forward questions to the appropriate bodies, particularly those responsible for applying the ethics policy for research involving humans and the intellectual property policy. Only data for which participants have given their consent for secondary use and that has been approved by the research ethics board may be shared.

